

Research Article

Effect of Different Pre-Treatment Methods on the Emergence and Early Growth of Soursop (*Annona muricata* L.)

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Abstract

The study examines the effect of different pre-treatment methods on the emergence of *Annona muricata*. The experiment was conducted within the premises of the Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria, Jericho, Ibadan. The experiment lasted for twelve weeks after planting. Thirty seeds were planted into a perforated bucket and the experimental design was laid down in Completely Randomize Design (CRD) with nine treatments and replicated 3 times. The treatments were T₁ which is the control, T₂, which is the beneath (lower part) mechanical scarification, T₃ mechanical scarification at the side, T₄ which is soaked in water for five days, T₅ which is soaked in water for seven days, T₆ which is acid scarification for 5 minutes, T₇ which is acid scarification for 10 minutes, T₈ which is acid scarification for 20 minutes, and T₉ which is acid scarification for 30 minutes. The acid used for the scarification is hydrochloric acid. The following parameters were assessed weekly for a period of twelve weeks; emergence rate, plant height and numbers of leave productions. At the end of the experiment T₂ and T₉ performed better, where the T₂, which is the beneath scarification gave the highest emergence percentage of 66.7%. The T₉, which is acid scarification for 30 minutes also performed better having an emergence percentage of 60.0%. Conclusively, the different pre-treatment seed method used had both positive and negative effects on the emergence of soursop. T₂ (beneath scarification) is best recommended for raising soursop.

Keyword: Emergency, Growth, Soursop, Pre-treatment, Seeds

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Introduction

Soursop is a native to Central America, the Caribbean and Northern South America, Columbia and Brazil, Mexico, Peru and Venezuela and some sub-Saharan African countries that lie within the tropics. In Nigeria it grows in every part of the country, commonly known as *shawashawa* or *shawa shop*. Soursop has a lot of medicinal benefits, from the skin, leaves and seeds which are used in preparing a traditional medicine for treating cancer, treating diabetes, disappearance of swollen around the cut on incision after surgery without producing a scar, it alleviates liver disease and leprosy, lower blood pressure, to sober a drunk person, and also serve as cough medicine, depression, stress, and normalize the nervous system that are less good (WHO, 1998). Soursop serves as drug for internal inflammation, throat, cure skin ulcers and boils, effective for back pain indigestion and piles and it increase stamina patient that are not easily lax. Research has shown that soursop is very rich in vitamin B1, B2, and C. The fruit makes an excellent drink or ice cream after straining, its white edible pulp contents 80% water, 2% protein, 18% carbohydrate; the seeds are flat, hard and contain all that can be used for paint or insecticide (Warrington 2003). A number of medicinal properties are attributed to the leaves and juice of the soursop. Toxic and insecticidal characteristics are reported for different parts of the tree and fruit. Soursop flowers and fruit during the month of April to October, it is truly tropical.

The optimal range of latitude is between 27°N and 22.5°S. It grows and produces well at 21 to 30°C, being very sensitive to severe changes in temperature, especially if the limit of 12°C is reached (Pinto and Silva, 1994). In Nigeria it is harvested when ripe, sliced into part and eaten directly from the inside and the seeds thrown away. It cannot be transported in large quantities to the market for commercial purpose, owing to the soft and irregular nature of the skin when ripe. It is susceptible to damage when heaped and also because of the sticky nature of the flesh, a crushed soursop fruit can be very messy (Singh, 1987).

Moreover, economic returns can be obtained in a short period of time since there is no need to wait for the plant to attain reproductive stage like in the case of production. Soursop seedlings are as a result of poor storability of the seeds. Soursop seed lose viability easily and do not store for a very long time. Soursop has thick black seed coat that reduces water inhabitation during the first stage of germination and therefore requires some pre-sowing treatment to enhance germination and seedlings emergence

(Van Doesburg, 1986). Immense medicinal properties, wide range of uses and its lucrative price, it would be great national importance to popularize this plant among farmers.

Hence, an investigation was conducted to evaluate various seed treatment techniques on the performance of soursop seedlings.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Site

The experiment was carried out at the ornamental nursery of Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria (FRIN), Ibadan. It is located in Ibadan North-West Local Government area of Oyo state. The climate condition of the area is tropically dominated by rainfall pattern ranging from 1400mm-1500mm; the average temperature is above 35.2 °C (FRIN, ANNUAL METROLOGICAL REPORT).

Procurement of Material

The fresh seed from healthy fruit (*Annona muricata*) was gotten from Oje market in Ibadan. The seeds were extracted from ripe soursop fruit and viability test was carried out by introducing the seeds into a bucket in clean water, the seed that sink were collected for scarification and consider having an active embryo, while the floated seeds were collected and thrown away. The top soil was gotten from Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria (FRIN), Ibadan. It was sieved with 2mm sieve into a bowl. The Nine treatments were arranged in Complete Randomized Design. The perforated bowl were filled with top soil, thirty seeds were sown in each bowl, arranged in rows in the nursery and watered every two days.

Method

The soursop seed was planted in nine (9) bucket and the soil was gotten from Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria.

Treatment Used

- T₁. The control
- T₂. Mechanical scarification at hilum below
- T₃- Mechanical scarification at the side
- T₄- Soaked in water for 5days
- T₅- Soaked in water for 7days
- T₆- Acid scarification for 5minutes

T₇-Acid scarification for 10minutes

T₈- Acid scarification for 20minutes

T₉- Acid scarification for 30minutes

Variables Assessed

Data collections commenced after two weeks and continued weekly. The following data were assessed:

Emergence Data: Numbers of plant that emerged for each week was counted and recorded

Numbers of leaves: Numbers of leave for each plant was counted and recorded

Plant Height: Plant height was measured by using a thread to measure the height before it was placed on a ruler for accurate readings, which was measure from the base of the seedlings to the apex of the main stem.

Top Soil Analysis

The physio-chemical analysis of the experimental soil for the experiment was carried out at Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria (FRIN).

Method of Data Analysis

Data were statistically analysed by two-way ANOVA. Mean differences were calculated for significance by using Duncan's test at $P \leq 0.05$ significant level.

Table 1: Chemical Laboratory Analysis of the top soil

Parameter	Value
%O.C	0.04
% O.M	3.51
%N	0.26
P (mg/kg)	5.04
Mn(mg/kg)	23.70
Fe (mg/kg)	26.00
Cu (mg/kg)	5.30
Zn(mg/kg)	2.20
Na(Cmol/kg)	1.90
K(Cmol/kg)	3.00
Mg(CMol/kg)	0.05
Ca(Cmol/kg)	3.00
%SAND	87.40
%CLAY	9.0
%SILT	3.5

Source: Bioscience Department Soil Laboratory, Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria

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Results and Discussions

T₂ (helium scarification) has best performance in terms of germination data of 15.75 in number which is followed by the T₉ (Acid scarification for 30 minutes) and T₅ (Soaked in water for 7 days) which also performed well in terms of emergence data of 11.75 in number. The least performance is T₁ (The control) which is 5.83 in number as presented in Table 2. The main purpose for this observation is to determine the treatment that have best performance and also any other treatment that perform well.

Table 2: Effect of Different Seed Treatment on the Emergence Data of *Annona muricata*

TRT	Weeks After Sowing						Mean
	3	4	5	6	7	8	
T ₁	5.00	3.50	4.00	4.50	7.00	11.00	5.83
T ₂	9.50	9.50	11.50	12.50	14.50	18.50	15.75
T ₃	6.50	13.00	11.00	10.50	13.00	14.00	11.42
T ₄	6.50	8.00	8.00	8.00	13.00	14.50	9.67
T ₅	6.50	8.00	12.00	13.00	14.50	16.50	11.75
T ₆	5.50	12.00	10.00	7.50	10.50	14.50	10.00
T ₇	2.50	10.50	9.50	9.50	14.00	16.50	10.42
T ₈	2.50	6.50	10.50	9.00	12.00	15.00	9.25
T ₉	4.00	7.00	14.00	14.50	16.50	18.50	12.42

Where,

TRT = Treatment

T₂ (helium below scarification) has the highest emergence percentage of 66.7% in terms of emergence percentage followed by T₉ (Acid scarification for 30 minutes) which also performed well in terms of emergence percentage of 60.0%. The least performance is T₁ (The control) with 33.3% as presented in Table 3. Aatla H.B and D. Srihari (2013) also carried out an experiment on the influence of pre-sowing treatment on emergence growth and vigour of mango.

Table 3: Effect of Different Seed Pre-Treatment on the Emergence Percentage on *Annona muricata*

TRT	Emergence (%)
T ₁	33.3
T ₂	66.7
T ₃	50.0
T ₄	50.0
T ₅	53.3
T ₆	46.7
T ₇	53.3
T ₈	46.7
T ₉	60.0

T₅ (Soaked in water for 7 days) had the highest number of leaf production with a value of 6.30, followed by T₄ (Soaked in water for 5 days) with a value of 6.00, while T₂ (Mechanical scarification at hilum below) has the value of 5.88. The least performance is T₁ which is the control with a value of 3.00.

Table 4: Effect of Different Seed Pre-Treatment on Leaf Production of *Annona muricata*

TRT	Weeks After Sowing				Mean
	9	10	11	12	
T ₁	1.00	2.00	3.00	4.00	3.00
T ₂	3.50	5.50	7.00	7.50	5.88
T ₃	2.50	5.50	6.00	8.50	5.63
T ₄	3.00	5.50	7.00	8.50	6.00
T ₅	4.00	6.00	7.00	8.00	6.30
T ₆	2.50	5.00	5.50	6.00	4.75
T ₇	3.50	5.00	6.00	7.50	5.50
T ₈	3.00	4.50	5.00	6.00	4.63
T ₉	3.00	5.00	6.00	7.00	5.25

Table 5 revealed that there is significant difference among the treatment at 5% level of probability which indicate the different seed treatments adopted gave significant effect on leaf production of soursop.

Table 5: Analysis Of Variance of Leaf Number

SV	DF	SS	MS	F	P-Value
TRT	8	34.00	4.2500	19.12	0.001
Error	9	2.00	0.2222		
Total	17	36.0			

Significant at 5% level of probability

T₂ (Mechanical scarification hilum below) gave the best result of 16.13cm in terms of plant height, followed by T₅ (Soaked in water for 7days) which has the value of 15.19cm, and T₉ (Acid scarification for 30 minutes) with the result of 14.90cm while the least performance is the T₁ (control) with the value of 6.75cm.

Table 6: Effect of Different Seed Pre-Treatment of Plant Height of *Annona muricata*

TRT	Weeks After Sowing				Mean
	9	10	11	12	
T ₁	4.75	6.25	7.25	8.75	6.75
T ₂	14.50	15.25	17.00	17.75	16.13
T ₃	11.00	14.00	16.75	17.50	14.81
T ₄	9.00	9.50	11.00	12.00	10.38
T ₅	12.60	14.25	16.40	17.50	15.19
T ₆	10.50	12.50	13.50	15.25	12.94
T ₇	11.15	14.00	16.20	18.00	14.84
T ₈	8.75	11.00	12.00	12.50	11.06
T ₉	10.75	14.35	16.75	17.75	14.90

Table 7 reveals that there is significant difference among the treatment at 5% level of probability which indicated the different seed pre-treatments adopted gave significant effect on plant height of *Annona muricata*.

Table 7: Analysis of Variance for Plant Height on *Annona muricata*

SVDF		SS	MS	F	P-Value
TRT	8	181.111	22.639	3.09	0.057
Error	9	66.000	7.333		
Total	17	247.111			

Significant at 5% level of probability

Conclusion

Based on the findings, *Annona muricata* responded positively to T₂ (hilum below scarification) and T₉ (Acid scarification for 30minute) in terms of emergence rate while T₇ gives better result in terms of plant height. T₂ (hilum below scarification) was the most economical, is therefore ideal for the best seed pre-treatment for emergence and also the safest method of scarifying soursop

References

- Aatla, H.B and Srihari D. (2013): Influence of pre- sowing treatments on the germination, growth and vigour of mango *Mangifera indicacv*.Alpkonso. *Asian J. Hort.*, 8(1): 122-125
- Pinto, T. (1994): Sour sop is cultivated from sea level to 1,200 altitude and between latitude 27° North and 22.5° south its northern extreme include Southern Florida (USA)Culiacan, Chiapas, Véreux and Yucatan (Mexico), Cuba and the South of China, White it is southern extreme is in Central Brazil.
- Singh, S., (1987): Effect of hot water and acid treatment on germination of *Cassia fistula* L. seeds. Proceedings of the International Symposium on Forest Seed Problems in Africa, August 23- September 2, 1987, Harare, Zimbabwe, pp: 321-323.
- Van Doesburg, P.H. (1986): Two insect pests of soursop in Surinam. *Carib. Agr.* 3(1): 797-803.
- Warrington, Ian J. (2003): "Annonaceae". Apples: Botany, Production and Uses. CABI Publishing: 04-20.

World Health Organization, (1998): Quality Control Methods for Medicinal Plant Material, Geneva, *A.T.T.B.S. Publishers.*: 28-33.